

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

Master of Information Systems

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**UPGRADING OF CLARK DEVELOPMENT CORPORATION ELECTRONIC
RECORDS MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**

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This Special Project titled
Upgrading of Clark Development Corporation Electronic Records
Management System

is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and
Communication Studies in partial fulfillment of the requirements for
the Master of Information Systems.

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ABSTRACT

In 2018, Clark Development Corporation (CDC) Records Management Division (RMD) implemented the Clark Development Corporation Electronic Records Management System (CDC-eRMS). The CDC-eRMS's objective was to automate some of the processes of RMD. For over 2 years of the system being implemented, RMD received some feedback and suggestions from the management and end-users. To address these, an upgrade to the existing system is needed.

This project is going to bring new features to the existing system such as customized GUI, streamlined workflow, notification through multiple communication channels, monitoring/tracking module and reporting dashboard. With these new features, CDCeRMS effectiveness is going to improve. The development of this project is done using a rapid development style of methodology which focuses on rapidly developing high quality software that meets the requirements of the users. One of the limitations of the system is that the system is dependent on the old system, so customization and adding of new features may become impossible or hard to implement in the future, especially if the current administrator of the system would leave without proper documentation of the system.

After the implementation of the proposed system, the feedback from the users has been good, especially the usability and simplicity of the system. With this feedback, the objective of the proposed system was met with satisfaction

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This page may be considered optional, but most theses and dissertations carry it for very good reasons. The acknowledgment page may be as brief as half a page, or as long as two pages. Who to acknowledge would depend on the decision of the author.

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Dedicated to:
Clark Development Corporation

Chapter I

Introduction

According to “tyrocity.com” Record management is the area of office management which deals with the maintenance of records of the organization. It is very important for management to control the records. It is the art of handling and maintaining office records from the time of creation to disposal. The records are systematically maintained to preserve them for future use. Record management refers to the activities designed to control the life cycle of a record [0].

The need for record(s) management is not an easy task. The bulk of data that needs to be organized must be given attention when it comes to speed and processing efficiency. In an organization, data needs to be catered to make sure the integrity is not compromised, and it is credible. Documents are very important for an organization and it needs to be managed, and automation is the key to achieving the goal. The research is focused on developing a system that will enhance the records management of Clark Development Corporation (CDC) Records Management Division (RMD).

THE PROBLEM DOMAIN

A. Statement of the Problem

In 2018, Clark Development Corporation (CDC) Records Management Division (RMD) launched its Electronic Records Management System (CDC-eRMS). The CDC-eRMS primary objective was to automate some of the manual processes of the RMD. Below are the current features of the CDC-eRMS:

- Processing of Incoming Documents
- Routing of Documents

- Archiving
- Email Notification
- Audit Trail
- Optical Character Recognition
- Stamping of Electronic Documents

While the implementation of CDC eRMS was successful, there are some suggestions and feedback from the users and management that must be addressed. These are the following:

- The Graphical User Interface is complex. There are too many available options to a user which they do not use.
- Notifications should also be sent using other communication channels such as SMS and Viber.
- VP/AVP/Managers should have a monitoring dashboard of letters they assigned to their subordinates.
- Call-up reminder to the user regarding the in-progress document's age.

With these suggestions and feedback, An improvement and upgrading of the current system are needed.

B. Background and Objectives of the Project

The project is initiated from the suggestions and feedback of the management and end-users. In order for the current system to provide better service to the corporation and to be compliant to ARTA in terms of document processing time, upgrading of the CDC eRMS is initiated by the Office of Primary Responsible (OPR) of the current system which is the RMD. The project objective is to improve the current system. The following features will be added:

- Simple and user-friendly web-based interface
- Monitoring/Tracking Dashboard
- Report Dashboard
- Sending of notifications through multiple communication channels
- Availability of report analytics on accounts of the management

C. Significance and Scope of the Project

The project will bring better service to the CDC Records Management Division, and to the corporation itself. The project will improve the effectiveness of the current system and enable the management to monitor the efficiency of their units.

The project will focus on upgrading the existing system to bring better services to the end-user by implementing their suggestions and improving the graphical user interface of the system. This project aims to create an improved version of the existing system while still having the functionalities of the old system.

D. Documentation of Existence and Seriousness of the Problem

- Documentation of the current system:
 - To prove the existence of the system, the following screenshots of the current system are provided:

● Problems identified with the existing system:

- After the current system has been implemented, RMD received feedbacks and suggestions from the end-users and management.

These are the following:

- The Graphical User Interface is complex.
- The system should be able to send notifications via SMS.
- The current system has no monitoring/tracking dashboard for assigned documents.
- The current system's notification message cannot be customized fully.
- End-users do not fully use/support the system which results in a long

pending time of documents in the system.

- Statistics and Report generated from the current system:

These are the following reports and statistic that the RMD generate using data from CDC-eRMS:

- Distribution of Profile
 - This report shows how the documents are distributed among the groups, departments, and divisions. Statistics and efficiency are also included in this report.

1. For Action Documents: 1160

Distribution Profile
January to April 2021

DEPARTMENT	Letters Received			Acted upon status			In progress status			Average Days In Progress
	No.	%	Ranking	No.	%	Average Processing Days	No.	%	Ranking	
Office of the President	41	4.31		36	88	1	5	12		1
Communications Division	3	0.32		1	33	4	2	67		22
Corporate Planning Division	10	1.05		10	100	7	0	0		
Information Technology Department	1	0.11		1	100	0	0	0		
Admin and Finance Group	6	0.63		3	50	2	3	50		20
Accounting Division	21	2.21	5	19	90	2	2	10		30
Administration Department	8	0.84		0	0		8	100		40
External Affairs Department	104	10.94		74	71	7	30	29		39
Human Resource Division	3	0.32		1	33	22	2	67		22
Property Management Division	11	1.16		6	55	3	5	45		18
Purchasing Division	2	0.21		0	0		2	100		11
Records Management Division	1	0.11		1	100		0	0		
Treasury Division	9			8		10	1			1
Business Development & Business	75	7.89		48	64	5	27	36		8
Environmental Permits Division	23	2.42		0	0		23	100		42
Health and Sanitation Division	15	1.58	3	0	0		15	100	2	52
Investment Promotions Division I	403	42.38		230	57	5	173	43		41
Investment Promotions Division II	172	18.09	1	169	98	7	3	2	1	25
Tourism Promotions Division	5	0.53		1	20	6	4	80		17
Trade Facilitation Division	32			0			32			47
Engineering Services Group	35	3.68		25	71	10	10	29		29
Building and Facilities Permits Division	43	4.52		17	40	9	26	60		34
Construction Management Division	9	0.95		7	78	11	2	22	4	48
Technical Services Department	2	0.21		2	100	2	0	0	5	
Security Services Group	11	1.16		6	55	15	5	45		27
Estate Preservation & Recovery	2	0.21	2	1	50	15	1	50	5	2
Public Safety Division	98	10.30	4	76	78	23	22	22	3	23
Legal Affairs Group	14	1.47		5	36	11	9	64		44
Corporate Services Division	1	0.11		1	100	11	0	0		
Total	1160			748		8.17	412			26.79

2. For Info Document :21

- Status Profile

- This report shows statistics of documents per status.

External Document Received through eRMS Status Profile

Month of January,February,March,April ; Year 2021

Chapter II

REVIEW OF EXISTING ALTERNATIVES

To cope with the problem, the RMD staff is doing their best to provide temporary or alternative solutions.

- Identified problems and Temporary solutions

1. Problem: The Graphical User Interface is complex or hard to understand

Temporary solution: Currently, the Records Management is doing their best to train each end-user on how to use the system and get familiar with it.

2. Problem: The current system cannot send notifications via SMS.

Temporary solution: Some of the notifications will be sent using 3rd party applications such as SMS Gateway API and Viber API.

3. Problem: The current system has no monitoring/tracking.

Temporary solution: RMD provides CDC groups, departments, and divisions reports on documents assigned to them through excel files.

The following systems can be considered alternatives to the existing system:

1. Alfresco
2. Dokyumento
3. Share point
4. Laserfiche

These 4 systems also have a records management system module and some of these systems are capable of solving some of the problems with the existing system but RMD cannot use these systems because of several reasons:

1. Budget - RMD can not request for a budget easily because they already have an existing system and they would need to justify first why they are replacing the existing system.
2. Utilize the existing system - The VP for AFG wants full utilization of the current system.
3. The systems above are not capable of implementing all the new features that are required to address the problems. Also, the customization of the systems above is limited.

The project Upgrading of Clark Development Corporation Electronic Records Management System's objective is to solve all the identified problems while still utilizing the existing system. This project is cost-effective (in-house development) and will improve the effectiveness of the system and the efficiency of the end-users.

Chapter III

PROJECT

DETAILS

A. Overview

- description of the proposed system, use case diagram

Upgrading of Clark Development Corporation's Electronic Records Management System

B. Theoretical Framework

Information System theory

In order to provide a general and comprehensive definition of IS success that covers different perspectives of evaluating information systems, DeLone and McLean reviewed the existing definitions of IS success and their corresponding measures and classified them into six major categories. Thus, they created a multidimensional measuring model with interdependencies between the different success categories [1].

Motivated by DeLone and McLean's call for further development and validation of their model, many researchers have attempted to extend or respecify the original model. Ten years after the publication of their first model and based on the evaluation of the many contributions to it, DeLone and McLean proposed an updated IS success model [2].

The updated model consists of six interrelated dimensions of IS success: information, system and service quality, (intention to) use, user satisfaction, and net benefits. The arrows demonstrate proposed associations between the success dimensions. The model can be interpreted as follows: A system can be evaluated in terms of information, system, and service quality; these characteristics affect the subsequent use or intention to use and user satisfaction. As a result of using the system, certain benefits will be achieved. The net benefits will (positively or negatively) influence user satisfaction and the further use of the information system

Schematic of theory

Information Systems Success Model (DeLone & McLean 1992)

Updated Information Systems Success Model (DeLone & McLean 2002,2003)

Rationale for the Framework

A system can be evaluated in terms of information, system, and service quality; these characteristics affect the subsequent use or intention to use and user satisfaction. As a result of using the system, certain benefits will be achieved. The net benefits will (positively or negatively) influence user satisfaction and the further use of the information system.

C. Technologies Used

- Application Layer, Database layer, Client layer

The technologies used in developing and implementing the system is divided in 2 parts:

- Front-end

- The front-end or the graphical user interface of the system will be developed and designed using the following technologies: Balsamiq for creating wireframes, HTML for the skeleton of the GUI, CSS, and Bootstrap for the styling and responsiveness.

- Back-end

- The backend of the system will be developed and implemented using the following technologies:

1. PHP is the programming language that will be used to develop the system. PHP is a widely used web programming technology/language. It powers 78.9% of websites on the internet. Unlike any other programming language, PHP is easy to learn and is very powerful for creating websites. Also, PHP has a huge community which makes finding solutions for a problem easy.

2. MySQL is the relational database that will be used for the database of the system. This RDBMS is great for small to large-size applications. It is easy to use and it runs on the SQL programming language.

3. Postman is a tool for testing APIs. This tool will be used to test the script/code that will be used to communicate with the existing system.

4. VMware will be used to create virtual machines for the implementation of the system. This virtualization software allows the IT administrators to maximize the available resources of their servers.

D. System Design

System Features

1. User-friendly web-based graphical user interface

- Rationale: One of the problems that the RMD receives from their end-user is that the GUI of the system is complex and there are too many options which are not needed, so a custom interface must be created, an interface that is user-friendly and easy for users to get familiar with.

2. Notification through SMS

- Rationale: Currently, the notifications are only being sent through email. The management wants another way to send notifications to users, especially when a letter is important. They suggested that notification should also be received via SMS.

3. Streamlined workflow/process

- Rationale: The current workflow that is being used in the current system has some steps that can be removed to improve the process. This will make the processing of documents in the system easier and faster.

4. Monitoring/Tracking Dashboard

- Rationale: Currently, Group/Department/Division Heads have no way of monitoring and tracking documents that they assigned to their subordinates. One of the AVP requested this feature. This feature will give them an idea on the status of documents that they assigned to their

subordinates. This can also help them to remind their subordinates to update action taken on the documents in their accounts.

5. Report/Statistics Dashboard

- Rationale: Currently, the RMD manually generates the reports and they are sending the reports through email every month. To reduce time spent on doing recurring reports, a reporting dashboard will be created. This report dashboard will be available in the account of every Group/Department/Division's Head.

Interface Design

The following image below is the mock-up design for the web-based system:

The image shows a web browser window with the address bar displaying "https://cdc-erms.ciark.com.ph". The main content area of the browser contains a login form titled "CDC eRMS". The form is centered and contains the following elements:

- Username**: A text input field.
- Poseword**: A text input field.
- Login**: A button.

This is the Login Page of the System

This is the landing page of the system. This is the page where all assigned documents are listed.

This is the page where the user can see all the information about a document and can preview the scanned copy of the document. This page is where user can update their action taken to the document.

A Web Page

https://cdc-erms.clark.com.ph

Monitoring/Tracking Dashboard

Control Number	Subject	Date Received (RMD)	Date Assigned to Unit	Status	Document Age	Assigned to
XD-21-0001	Request for Inspection	06-05-2021	06-06-2021	Acted upon		
XD-21-0005	Request for Bring-in Permit	06-05-2021	06-07-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0008	Notice of Meeting	06-05-2021	06-06-2021	For Info		
XD-21-0021	Request for endorsement	06-06-2021	06-06-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0022	Vehicle Clearance	06-06-2021	06-08-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0031	Request for Fire Inspection	06-06-2021	06-08-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0035	Request for Fire Inspection	06-07-2021	06-07-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0040	Request for Exit Pass	06-07-2021	06-09-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0041	Request for Endorsement	06-07-2021	06-09-2021	In-progress		
XD-21-0042	Request to waive penalty	06-07-2021	06-08-2021	In-progress		

< / 10 >

This is the page where the management can view statistics and reports about the documents that were assigned to them.

Process flow/Workflow

System Architecture

E. Implementation

In developing the system, the programmer will follow a specific type of agile software development framework which is the extreme programming (XP) methodology. This methodology is the best approach for developing the system because changes in the system requirements during the development phase can be adapted easily. Also, this methodology works perfectly for this project because there will be less process that the developer would need to do thus making the development faster and more efficient.

In implementing the system, Parallel implementation methods will be used. This type of implementation will allow unhindered processing of documents while slowly transitioning to the new system. One of the main advantages of this method of implementation is that bugs that would occur during the parallel implementation can

be discovered and fixed immediately without stopping the operation.

Chapter IV

PROJECT ASSESSMENT

A. User Testing

The testing of the system will be done by RMD's staff while assessment and approval to deploy and use the system will be done by RMD's Manager and VP for AFG. Bug fixing and system modification based on the input of testers will be done after all the comments are consolidated.

The users were given a survey to evaluate the functionalities and features of the system. The users were given the system to explore the behavior.

While the system is being developed the common errors or bugs are logical errors when it comes to functions and features. It also includes database connectivity table field mismatch, data retrieval, and report generation. With the help of the users, the system was evaluated. The users participated in the dry run and they were able to assess the functionalities and operation of the system.

For user acceptance, the Manager of the Records Management Division assessed and evaluated the system. The Manager issued a certification of completion and acceptance to the proponent. See Appendix A.

B. Testing Results

Survey Questions

Measurement:

1 – Strongly Disagree

2 – Disagree

3 – Neutral

4 – Agree

5 – Strongly

Agree R –

Respondent Q -

Question

Question 1	The user interface is user-friendly
Question 2	The user interface is easy to navigate
Question 3	The system is easier to use compared to the old system
Question 4	The options/buttons are clear and can be easily located (i.e. logout button, links and etc.)
Question 5	The system is accessible across different browsers
Question 6	Users are able to monitor/track the documents assigned to their office through the system
Question 7	The system is able to notify (sms) users of in-progress documents that exceeded the standard time of action
Question 8	Reports are easy to access

Q	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q5	Q6	Q7	Q8
R1	4	4	5	4	5	4	4	4
R2	5	4	5	4	5	4	4	4
R3	4	4	5	5	5	4	4	4
R4	4	4	4	4	5	4	4	4
R5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
R6	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4

	1	2	3	4	5	Details
Q1	0	0	0	4	2	Four responded to Agreed and Two Strongly Agreed.
Q2	0	0	0	5	1	Five responded to Agreed and One Strongly Agreed.
Q3	0	0	0	2	4	Two responded to Agreed and Four Strongly Agreed.
Q4	0	0	0	4	2	Four responded to Agreed and Two Strongly Agreed.
Q5	0	0	0	1	5	One responded to Agreed and Five Strongly Agreed.
Q7	0	0	0	6	0	Six responded to Agreed..
Q8	0	0	0	6	0	Six responded to Agreed.
Q9	0	0	0	6	0	Six responded to Agreed.
T_Ave	0	0	0	34	14	

DISCUSSIONS

What are the things you learned as you did this project? What are the challenges that you encountered? Share relevant insights.

Building this project from start to finish has taught me a lot of things. From planning up to implementation, it has been a fruitful experience because I was able to apply all the things that I learned in the previous years such as Web Development, Programming, Project Strategic Planning, Database Design, and Project documentation. I was also able to learn new things such as working with web service, consuming and passing data from application to application, adding interaction in the project with the use of javascript, setting up virtual machines and web servers. Building a project alone comes with many challenges. I had a hard time learning the structure, architecture, and documentation of the web services of our old system. Their documentation available on the internet is limited and not easy to understand especially to those people that are new to the concept of web services. I also found it challenging to learn javascript because I don't have much experience working with this language. Overall, This project is the result of all the things that I learned. I was able to apply and practice the skills that I acquired in the previous year.

Maintenance Plan

The document and code of the project will be turned over to the office of the Records Management Division (RMD). One of the IT Staff of RMD which is also the programmer will be in charge of the maintenance of the project. Adding new features, fixing bugs, and Updating the system will be done by the IT Staff of RMD.

Chapter VI

CONCLUSION

As stated in the objectives. The project is initiated from the suggestions and feedback of the management and end-users. In order for the current system to provide better service to the corporation and to be compliant to ARTA in terms of document processing time, upgrading of the CDC eRMS is initiated by the Office of Primary Responsible (OPR) of the current system which is the RMD. The project objective is to improve the current system.

The following items will be part of the upgrading of CDC eRMS:

- Simple and user-friendly web-based interface
- Monitoring/Tracking Dashboard
- Report Dashboard
- Sending of notifications through multiple communication channels
- Availability of report analytics on accounts of managements

-Intended users: All employees of CDC whose position is supervisor up Providing a system for all CDC employees for better records management will improve their operations. It will give them a secure, efficient, and faster way of processing their information like retrieval, report generation in a short amount of time.

Chapter VII

FUTURE WORK

For future works, the following are intended:

- Make data privacy material available to users by including a page in the system intended for data privacy.
- Include sending of Statement of Accounts of Locators stored in the repositories of RMD as records
- Include a dashboard of activity in the accounts of end-user

The research will also be the basis for future studies. There is always room for improvement and hopefully, a better version of the system will be created as part of the improvement of the system. Future researchers could include the study as part of their literature. The study can become the basis for designers, developers, and researchers to improve and make an updated and better version of the system.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: User Acceptance Certification

CERTIFICATION OF COMPLETION AND ACCEPTANCE

This is to certify Mr. Sean Mitchell Y. Tolentino has completed the project "Upgrading of Clark Development Corporation Electronic Records Management System" which was evaluated on 05 January 2022.

This is to further certify that the required outputs have been verified and fully accepted by the Manager of Records Management Division.

Issued on the 05th day of January 2022 in Clark Freeport Zone, 2023 Philippines.

Certified by:

JOSEPHINE V. POYAOAN
Manager, Records Management Division

"A proud member of the BCDA group"

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Appendix B: Github Link to the code

- <https://github.com/seanmi/upgraded-erms>